

PEDAGOGICAL POSSIBILITIES OF APPLYING INNOVATION IN EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The implementation of innovations in the field of education is considered to depend on innovations and is expressed in modern concepts. Therefore, the article tried to reveal the possibilities of using pedagogical innovations.*

Keywords: *science and educational innovation, researchers of innovative processes, innovative activity, pedagogical innovation.*

Implementation of reforms in the education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan is becoming the priority goal of today. In particular, education Innovation (innovation in English) is considered as the basis of scientific research in the development of sciences. Innovation in science and education means appropriate changes that introduce a new, relatively stable element to a certain social unit - organization, population, society, group. It reveals the possibilities of modern science technologies, reflected in the specific activity system of the innovator.

Innovative technologies in education are innovations and changes in the pedagogical process and the activities of teachers and students, and interactive methods are fully used in its implementation. Interactive methods are called group thinking, that is, they are methods of pedagogical influence and are highly expressed in the content of education. The peculiarity of pedagogical methods is that they are implemented only through the collaborative activity of the pedagogue and students.

The process of pedagogical cooperation in the educational system has its own character and is explained in the following:

- To increase the activity of the student during the lesson, to teach independent thinking, creativity and research;

- To increase students' interest in learning in the educational process;

- To improve the student's ability to work independently;

Tasks such as the organization of regular cooperation activities between the teacher and the student take place and are considered effective. The researchers A. Prigozhin, B.V. Sazonov, V.S. Tolstoy, A.G. Kruglikov, A.S. Axiezer, and N.P. Stepanov have based the scientific study of this problem on the basis of two approaches to the study of innovative processes: the interaction of a particular form of innovation is introduced through practical discovery. is given.

In the first approach, some new idea introduced into life is described. In the next approach, it is the interaction of innovations, their integrity, competition and consequences that replace one of them with the other. Scientists distinguish between the concept of periodicity of life during innovation analysis. This concept stems from the fact that innovation is a process.

In the literature on pedagogy, a clear scheme of the innovation process is given. It covers the following steps:

1. The stage of the birth of a new idea or the emergence of a new concept. It is also referred to as the discovery stage in the sources.

2. Inventing, that is, the stage of creating something new.

3. The stage of knowing how to apply the created innovation in practice.
4. The stage of spreading the news around and applying it widely.
5. The stage of dominance of innovation in a certain field. At this stage, the novelty loses its novelty, and its effective alternative appears.
6. Based on a new alternative, it consists of the stage of reducing the scope of the innovation through replacement.

V.A. Slastyonin considers innovation to be a set of purpose-oriented innovation creation, wide dissemination and use process, and its purpose is to satisfy people's needs and aspirations with new means.

The authors of the systematic concept of innovation A.I. Prigozhin, B.V. Sazonov, V.S. Tolstoy distinguish two important forms of innovative processes.

An innovation to the first form is introduced as a simple development. This applies to organizations that have adopted the product for the first time. The second form depends on the large-scale development of the novelty.

Innovation is also considered as an internal logic, as a dynamic system that develops legitimately over time and expresses its interaction with the environment. The concept of "new" occupies a central place in pedagogical innovation. It also arouses interest in special, conditional, local and subjective innovation in pedagogical science. According to V.A. Slastenin, about the special innovation, the current modernization envisages updating one of the elements of a specific system product. Conditional innovation is a combination of certain elements that lead to complex and progressive innovation.

Local novelty is determined by the use of novelty in a concrete object.

The concepts of novelty and innovation are mutually different in scientific directions.

Innovation is a tool: it is reflected in a new method, methodology, technology, etc. V.I. Zagvyazinsky defined the new concept and said that the new in pedagogy is not only an idea, but also approaches, methods, and technologies that have not yet been used. But the elements of this pedagogical process are complex or separately taken elements, and reflect the advanced beginnings of effectively solving educational tasks in changing conditions and situations.

R. N. Yusufbekova expresses the content of pedagogical reality that can change, leading to pedagogical innovation, previously unknown and previously unrecorded situation, result, developing theory and practice.

In pedagogical innovation, R. N. Yusufbekova distinguishes three blocks of the structure of the innovation process:

The first block is the separation of new ideas in pedagogy. This includes the classification of new, pedagogical innovation in pedagogy, conditions for creating innovation, norms of innovation, preparation for mastering and using innovation, traditional approach and innovative ability, stages of creating innovation in pedagogy.

The second block consists of experiencing newness and acquiring knowledge.

The third assessment determines the diversity of processes of block-pedagogical organizations, evaluation of newness and acquired knowledge, conservatism and innovation in pedagogy, innovation environment, readiness to perceive and evaluate new things in pedagogical communities.

The fourth block is the use of innovation and its implementation, i.e., the types of laws of its effective use and wide implementation during the implementation of the innovation. M.M.

Potashnik's opinion about innovation processes attracts attention. He describes the innovation process as follows:

- as an activity structure; motive, goal, task, content, form, methods, set of methodical components.

- as a subjective structure; is reflected in innovative activity entities, regional organizations, districts, cities and other regions.

- as meaningful structures; creation, development and assimilation of innovations in educational and educational work, management;

- as a periodic structure based on gradation; It consists of the emergence of innovation, rapid growth, maturity, assimilation, diffusion (absorption, spread), enrichment (saturation), backwardness - crisis, deception, modernization.

- as a management structure; consists of interaction of 4 types of management actions, i.e. planning, organization, leadership, control.

- as an organizational structure; It is reflected in diagnosis, pre-possession, pure organizational behavior, practical, generalizing, implementing behavior.

The innovation process consists of a system that includes structural structures and laws.

In the literature on pedagogy, 4 main laws of the innovation process are distinguished:

- the law of ruthless disorder of the pedagogical innovation environment;
- the law of molding (stereotyping);
- the law of periodic repetition and return of pedagogical innovation.

In the law of unruly chaos, holistic ideas about pedagogical processes and events are broken, pedagogical consciousness is divided, pedagogical innovation is evaluated and the importance of innovation is widely spread.

The law of modeling (stereotyping) is that pedagogical innovation has a tendency to stereotype thinking and move to practical action. In such a case, the pedagogical pattern (stereotype) is forced to lag behind and become an obstacle to the implementation of other innovations.

The essence of the law of periodic repetition and return of pedagogical innovation is that innovation is renewed in new conditions.

Pedagogical innovation researchers distinguish two types of innovation process:

- The first type of innovation is spontaneous, that is, the need for it is not taken into account in the innovation process, there is no conscious attitude to the system, methods and ways of all the conditions for its implementation.

- The second type of innovation is the product of conscious, purposeful, scientifically based activity.

Innovative processes in the higher school were researched by V.A.Slastenin, M.M.Levina, M.Ya.Vilensky and others.

The higher school is based on the following approaches based on innovative processes:

- approach in terms of cultural studies (the priority development of human knowledge);
- approach in terms of personal activity (new technologies in education);
- subjective (dialogic) approach, i.e. humanization of professional training;
- conducting scientific research based on an individual-creative approach, interaction between teachers and students.

The subject of innovative activity in the higher school is the teacher and his personal opportunity. Socio-cultural, intellectual and moral capabilities of the teacher are of great importance.

The important elements of the innovative pedagogical process are self-management and self-mobilization of the individual. One of its most important areas is the development of cognitive activity of students.

This direction includes the activity of activating students' academic work, determining their professional specialization.

The integration of education, science and production as the main directions requires a transition to new principles in their interaction.

Based on the analysis of the theory of innovative activity factors, the basis of these concepts leads to the conclusion that its most important direction is humanistic axiology.

The axiological approach to innovative activity means that a person contributes to the process of creating new things, pedagogical values created by him. Axiology considers man as the highest value and the only goal of social progress. The innovative activity of the teacher is considered as a creative process and a result of creative activity.

REFERENCES

1. Sh.M. Mirziyoyev "Strategy of New Uzbekistan" Tashkent-2021, 128b.
2. Sh.M. Mirziyoyev "The work of a people with great intention will be great, life will be bright and the future will be prosperous" T:2019, "Uzbekistan", 400b.
3. Bordovskoy N.V. Modern educational technologies: textbook / team of authors/ - 2nd edition, deleted - M.: KNORUS, 2011. - 432 p.
4. Ishmukhamedov R, Yuldashev M "Innovative pedagogical technologies in education and training" Tashkent: 2013, 279 p.
5. A.R.Rakhmonov "Pedagogical education as a result of the new stage of renaissance in innovation cluster educational institutions". Mughallim khem zulziziz bilimlendaro' №5 2022 jyl ISSN 2181-7138 Scientific-methodological journal. 67-71. (25.10. 2007 #138).